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NEW SURVEY AND TYPOLOGICAL STUDY OF PREHISTORIC WARES OF DUTLUCA REGION, UŞAK, TURKEY

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ABSTRACT

Dutluca region is a location in central-west Anatolia that has not been surveyed much. The presence of a ceramic different from Hacilar and Lakes Region Early Chalcolithic painted wares was mentioned in Dutluca, which was first referred to by J. Mellaart. However, there is no detailed information. In the surveys we conducted in 2018 and 2019, two prehistoric settlements were revealed in Dutluca region. These are Dutluca Mound and Adatepe. Dutluca Mound is a settlement that started from the Early Neolithic period and continued until today. Adatepe, on the other hand, is a tophill settlement that was inhabited in Neolithic and Chalcolithic period. In the Neolithic period, monochrome pottery is generally similar.. The painted wares of Hacilar are seen in a wide area in Southwest Anatolia. Paint decorated ware has an important place in dating the Early Chalcolithic Age ceramics. Especially the Early Chalcolithic painted sherds of Adatepe is important in terms of representing a tradition different from that of Hacilar painted sherds. Painted wares of the Dutluca region differ from those of Hacilar. This separation is due to the different paint decorations. In addition, the pits identified on Adatepe are not available anywhere else for now. The spread of Hacilar culture in the south of Western Anatolia and the spread of Fikirtepe culture in the north is evident. The presence of painted wares in Dutluca, which is located between these two cultural regions, is also important for understanding the cultural development process in Western Anatolia in the Early Chalcolithic Age and for establishing inter-regional relations. In the context of the Early Chalcolithic Age, it can be concluded that the Dutluca region can be considered as a separate cultural region such as the Lakes Region, Fikirtepe, and the West Anatolian shores. This manuscript evaluates Dutluca region and explains the prehistory of the region and the significance of Early Chalcolithic wares in detail.

KEYWORDS: Dutluca, Adatepe, Neolithic, Chalcolithic, Painted wares, Western Anatolia, Turkey

1. INTRODUCTION

Important data were obtained during the archaeological excavations and surveys on Neolithic and Chalcolithic period in Western Anatolia. The excavations carried out in Ulucak, Dedecik-Heybelitepe, Ege Gübre, Yeşilova shed light on regional relations by revealing the cultural status of West Anatolian coasts in 7000-6000 B.C.E (Çilingiroğlu and Çilingiroğlu, 2007) (Fig. 1).

The chronology of the Neolithic and Chalcolithic ages could not be determined exactly in these centers

where excavations were carried out on the western Anatolian coasts. The situation of the pre-pottery Neolithic phase of the Neolithic age is uncertain. It is also unclear how the transition from the Neolithic age to the Chalcolithic age took place. In addition, the distinction between Neolithic and Chalcolithic ages cannot be made exactly. The known fact is that the use of pottery is increasing in the Neolithic era. It is observed that mineral-added red, cream and brown pottery is a common feature in settlements in the Western Anatolia region.

Figure 1. Western Anatolian Settlements.

It is controversial when the Neolithic era began and when it ended on the Western Anatolian coast. The transition from the Neolithic Age to the Chalcolithic Age was accepted as 6000 BC. The term Late Neolithic-Early Chalcolithic, which is used for the cultural process between 6000 and 5700 BC in Western Anatolia, shows that Neolithic traditions continue in the region (Çevik and Erdoğan, 2020).

Early Neolithic pottery in Western Anatolia is cream and brown slipped and burnished, and there are S-profile forms with lugs with tube holes. The excavations carried out in the Late Neolithic Period show that the culture from the past developed and continued in 6000 BC. Red slipped and burnished pottery is seen throughout the region. Although the decoration is not common, there are a small number of impresso and paint decorated pottery (Erdoğan and Çevik, 2020).

Starting from 6000 BC, new elements added to the material culture can be mentioned rather than a radical change in the region. In this process, it is understood that Western Anatolia has entered into a wider communication network with other regions of Anatolia. In the Early Chalcolithic Period, between 5600-5500 BC, a sharp cultural change is observed in all of Western Anatolia. There has been a radical change in settlement systems, architecture, pottery and other finds (Çevik and Erdoğan, 2019).

Our knowledge of the end of the Chalcolithic Age in Western Anatolia is extremely limited. In this period when urbanization started, it is not possible to talk about developed cultures for the Western Anatolian coastal regions. In this period, highly developed cultures containing rich finds are seen in Mesopotamia, Balkans and Continent Greece (Çevik and Erdoğan, 2019).

In the city of Uşak, located in central-west Anatolia, no excavations of the prehistoric period have been

carried out so far. While important excavation activities were carried out in the surrounding areas, not much interest has been shown to Uşak. Considering the lack of prehistoric surveys in Uşak, our surveys were started in the area.

The Early Bronze Age (EBA) surveys we started in Uşak city in 2013 with the permission of the Ministry of Culture and Tourism, General Directorate of Cultural Heritage and Museums are still on-going (Oy, 2018). During these surveys, not only Neolithic and Chalcolithic settlements of EBA but also of the earlier periods in the area were found (Oy, 2017; Oy 2019). In addition, the settlements of other periods were also examined.

Uşak city is located at an important point due to its connection to Gediz River (Hermos) and Büyük Menderes River (Meander/Maiandros), which are among the natural routes of West Anatolia. Culturally, it is between Fikirtepe culture in the north and Hacilar culture in the south. It is also between the Central Anatolia (Çatalhöyük) in the east and the western Anatolia coast. Early settlements and surveys carried out in Uşak region are important for revealing the relationships with these cultural regions and understanding the Neolithic and Chalcolithic cultures.

Thanks to Middle Palaeolithic finds (250.000-60.000 B.C.E) at Sürmecik location in Uşak Banaz, new clues have begun to emerge about the early periods of the region (Dağcı et al., 2017). The earliest settlement in Uşak dates back to Middle Palaeolithic period for now. Although the prehistory of the region after Palaeolithic period is unknown, a small number of Neolithic and Chalcolithic Age settlements were found as a result of the surveys we started in Uşak in 2013. A large increase was achieved in the number of settlements in the region in EBA. Neolithic and Chalcolithic Age settlements in Uşak have revealed findings that will show relations with other centres in West Anatolia. However, especially the Early Chalcolithic Age painted wares in settlements of Dutluca village in the south of Uşak city are remarkable for showing a different development. Indeed, it has been stated in the surveys of J. Mellaart and his evaluations about Dutluca that this place was different. Since no detailed information was given, our surveys concentrated on this place.

There are two prehistoric settlements in Dutluca. These are Dutluca mound in Dutluca village and Adatepe location on the bank of Yavu Stream. There are also some prehistoric settlements nearby, especially Köselier Mound. These settlements were examined in detailed with our team in our level surveys during 2018-2019.

James Mellaart was the first to mention and draw attention to Dutluca, which was evaluated in this article. He mentioned a different ware group from Hacilar that he called Dutluca wares. Later, they were not emphasized much or they escaped from attention. J. Mellaart showed and mentioned Dutluca as a separate region specifically, but did not give detailed information. Later, Dutluca was forgotten. In our researches in the region, we conducted detailed surveys in Dutluca. These surveys were carried out by taking into consideration the presence of two prehistoric settlements in Dutluca and other settlements nearby such as Köselier mound.

Dutluca Höyük is a flat area and Adatepe is settlements on a natural hill. Due to the 3 km distance between them, it stands out in the region where they are connected to each other. It has been revealed that settlement in Dutluca started from the Early Neolithic Age. The pits on the Adatepe settlement have not been identified elsewhere before. The difference of the Early Chalcolithic Age painted wares reveals a different development from other regions in Western Anatolia during this period.

In the context of the location of Dutluca and Adatepe settlements in Western Anatolia and the characteristics of these settlements, the settlement process starting from the Early Neolithic age in the region will be put forward and explained. Especially, it is aimed to evaluate the painted wares dating to the Early Chalcolithic Age and to evaluate them with other regions.

2. DUTLUCA MOUND

Dutluca Mound is on the North of Uşak city, which is in Middle West Anatolia. Dutluca Mound is in Dutluca/Tutluca village which is 22 km south of Uşak city centre. It is 10 km to Ulubey town. Ulubey canyon, which is one of the largest canyons in the world, is within the village borders.

Dutluca Mound spreads over a large area next to the village and on the west of the village cemetery (altitude 846 m). The diameter of the settlement is 150 m, while its height is about 15 m. Agriculture is carried out on the mound and on the skirts of the mound. For this reason, its altitude is gradually decreasing. Neolithic, Chalcolithic, Early Bronze Age (EBA), Middle Bronze Age (MBA), Late Bronze Age (LBA), Roman sherds and obsidian and flint sharp objects and chips were found in the settlement. There are bowls, pots, three legged wares, tubular lugs and ribbed and decorated shreds of EBA intensively (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Dutluca and Adatepe flint tools and stone axe.

Figure 3. Photomicrograph from the (a) fine-grained obsidian and (b) flintstone rocks.

Obsidian occurred as a natural glass formed by the rapid cooling of viscous lava from volcanoes, which consist extremely rich in silica. They display mainly holohyaline texture consisting of quartz, plagioclase and minor brown mica (biotite) phenocrysts within a glassy matrix of the same minerals (Fig 3a). In some of these rocks, the presence of hematite (Fe_2O_3) produces red and brown varieties. Flintstone, chert, quartzite, these rocks consisting almost entirely of microcrystalline and/or cryptocrystalline crystals of quartz (SiO_2), and coarse-grained quartz minerals are anhedral, deformed grains with undulose extinction (Fig. 3b).

There is evidence that obsidian, which existed in the centers in Western Anatolia in the Neolithic Age, was obtained from two different regions, Melos Island and Cappadocia (Bostancı, 2020). Especially in Çukuriçi Höyük, obsidian originating from Melos Island was used (Guilbeau et. al., 2019). In Ulucak Höyük, obsidian originating from Melos was used (Çilingiroğlu, 2009). The Aegean relations of Ulucak Höyük can be seen since Neolithic times (Liritzis, 2005). The use of Melos obsidians in the settlements

on the Western Anatolian coast is an important situation showing the relations in the Aegean (Stevenson et. al., 2002; Bostancı, 2020).

In our surveys, Neolithic and Chalcolithic shreds were found especially in the North of the settlement. The reason for this is that the lower culture layers were destroyed due to agricultural activities in the North. Dutluca gives rich finds in terms of EBA and it is a large settlement. EBA sherds are found throughout the settlement. MBA and LBA sherds were found at the top of the settlement.

In the area where the old primary school building is located in Dutluca village, there are architectural pieces (some of which are inscribed), some columns and the head of a Corinthian column in the village's old fountain, which is still used today. There are similar finds in and around the village. All these are important in terms of showing a continuous settlement in Dutluca starting from the Neolithic period to the present day (Oy et al., 2019). J. Mellaart examined the Dutluca mound which he referred to as Dutluca wares. However, he did not state whether he was speaking of Dutluca or another settlement Adatepe, or both.

2.1. Neolithic and Chalcolithic Age (No: 1-25)

When In the surveys we conducted in Dutluca mound, earliest Neolithic and Chalcolithic Age sherds were found, especially in the north of the settlement. There are no previous findings of this period in the settlement. Our findings result from the fact that lower early layers were reached as a result of field ploughing in the north of the settlement. Although not in large numbers, Neolithic and Chalcolithic Age sherds were found in the settlement. This situation is important in terms of revealing the past of the settlement, which is going back to Neolithic period for now. Since the main floor is not reached completely, it should also be considered that there are layers going back to earlier periods in the settlement. Although in small numbers, monochrome and polychrome pottery were found in Dutluca mound.

2.1.1. Ware groups

Neolithic and Chalcolithic Age monochrome wares (no: 1-25) have dark surface and they generally consist of brown slipped wares (Fig. 4). There are also red and grey wares to a lesser extent. Some of the red slipped wares are purplish red slipped. Cream-pink slipped wares generally have painted decorations. The paste is mostly brown and grey. There are also red and pink paste wares in fewer numbers. The least found is black paste. This group of wares is hand-made, well baked and burnished. Almost all of them have mica additives. Half of them have lime additive, while 1/ 4 have plant additives. Although monochrome wares were found predominantly, polychrome samples were also found (no: 6, 8). These are cream with red paint decorations on them. Those with paint decoration near the bottom are painted red brown on cream (no: 22-23).

Figure 4. Dutluca Mound Neolithic and Chalcolithic sherds.

2.1.2. Forms (No: 1-25)

Although there is not much form variety among monochrome sherds, there are open forms belonging to bowls and pottery - open vessels (no: 1-4), closed forms (no: 5-8), flaring rim and deep forms (no: 9-15).

While they are generally plain, there are also examples with vertical relief decorations (no: 5) and painted decorations (no: 6, 8). There are also tubular lugs (no: 16-19), vertical lug (no: 20) and vertical decorated lugs (no: 21). The bases are flat (no: 22-25) and some have painted decorations (no: 22-23) (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Dutluca Mound Neolithic and Chalcolithic sherds.

Similar open forms (no: 1-4) are found in Yeşilova Mound on the shores of West Anatolia layer III 8-7 (Neolithic 6400-6100 B.C.E) (Derin et al., 2009), Ege Gübre III Neolithic layers (Ozan, 2012), Coşkuntepe (Takaoğlu, 2005), sherds dated back to 6000-5700 B.C.E, Ekşi Mound in up Meander Valley (Dedeoğlu et al., 2017), Höyücek Late Neolithic (LN) in Lakes Region (Duru and Umurtak, 2005), Kuruçay layer 13 (EN) (Duru, 1994). Similar closed forms (no: 5-8) are found in Yeşilova Mound layer III 5 (Neolithic 6000 B.C.E) (Derin et al., 2009), Fındık Kayabaşı Neolithic (Efe, 1995). Closed and band paint decorated sample (no: 6) is similar to Hacılar VII (LN) (Mellaart, 1970), Kuruçay layer 13 and 12 Early Neolithic (EN) form (Duru, 1994).

Similar flaring rim and deep forms (no: 9-15) are found in Ulucak level V (Abay, 2005), Ege Gübre Neolithic III (Ozan 2012), Asmainler Early Chalcolithic (EC) pottery (Efe, 1989-1990), Manisa region (Akdeniz, 2011), Ekşi Mound 6400-6000 B.C.E dated sherds (Dedeoğlu et al., 2017), Kuruçay level 13 (EN) (Duru, 1994), Çatalhöyük Late Neolithic (6400/6300-6000 B.C.E) (Özdöl Kutlu, 2014), Can Hasan layers 7-4 (LN) (French, 2005).

Similar tubular lugs (no: 16-19) are found in Yeşilova Höyük Neolithic level III lugs (6400-5800

B.C.E) (Derin et al., 2009; Derin, 2012), Ulucak V (Çilingiroğlu, 2012; Çilingiroğlu et al., 2012), Ege Gübre III Neolithic (Ozan, 2012), Coşkuntepe (Takaoğlu, 2005), Ekşi mound sherds dated back to 6400-6000 B.C.E (Dedeoğlu et al., 2017), Manisa region (Akdeniz, 2011), Höyücek Early Neolithic (Duru and Umurtak, 2005), Kuruçay layer 12 (EN) (Duru, 1994), Hacılar IX-VI (LN) (Mellaart, 1970).

Similar vertical lugs (no: 20) were found in Kuruçay layer 11 (LN) (Duru, 1994), similar vertical decorated lugs (no: 21) were found in Yeşilova mound layer II (Chalcolithic 4340-4230 B.C.E) (Derin et al., 2009), Manisa/Akhisar region Middle Chalcolithic age lugs (Takaoğlu, 2017), Laodikeia/Asopos hill VIIb Chalcolithic age lugs (5000 B.C.E) (Konakçı, 2016), similar bases (no: 22-25) were found in Yeşilova mound layer III. 8 (Neolithic 6490-6250 B.C.E) (Derin et al., 2009), Ege Gübre III Neolithic (Ozan, 2012), Manisa region (Akdeniz, 2011), up Meander valley settlements (Dedeoğlu, 2014), Ekşi mound 6000-5700 B.C.E dated sherds (Dedeoğlu et al., 2017), Selcen-Örenarası (Dedeoğlu and Ozan, 2016), Höyücek Late Neolithic (Duru and Umurtak, 2005), Kuruçay layer 11 (Duru, 1994). Chronological table of some of Neolithic settlements are given in the table 1.

Table 1. Chronological table of Neolithic and Chalcolithic settlements of layers.

Site	Early Chalcolithic 5000-5500 BC	Late Neolithic 6000-6600 BC	Early Neolithic 6600-7000 BC	References
Coşkuntepe		6000BC		(Takaoğlu, 2005)
Ulucak	IV (5600-6000BC)	V (6000-6600BC)	VI (6530-6850BC)	(Çilingiroğlu, 2012)
Ege Gübre	III (5800-6000BC)	IV (6000-6230BC)		(Ozan, 2012)
Yeşilova	III 1-2 (6000-5800BC)	III 8-3 (6000-6490BC)		(Derin et al., 2009)
Çukuriçi		VIII. (6000BC)	XII (6600BC)	(Horejs, 2012)
Ekşi Mound		5700-6700BC		(Dedeoğlu et al., 2017)
Selcen Örenarası		6400-6000BC		(Dedeoğlu and Ozan, 2016)
Hacılar	I (5700-5900BC)	II (5900-6200BC)	VI-IX (6000-7000BC)	(Mellaart, 1970)
Kuruçay	7 (5000-5300BC)	11 (5800-6000BC)	12-13 (6070-6230BC)	(Duru, 1994)
Höyücek		EYD(6300BC)	TD (6400BC)	(Duru and Umurtak, 2005)
Çatalhöyük		VI-VIII (6400-6700BC)	IX-XI (6800-7300BC)	(Özdöl Kutlu, 2014)
Can Hasan	II (5500-6000BC)			(French, 2005)

2.2. Early Bronze Age (No: 26-58)

There are mainly EBA sherds in Dutluca mound. EBA sherds vary in form and decoration. In addition to plain ones, there are also too many decorated sherds.

2.2.1. Wares

EBA wares have brown, grey and red slips. There are also black slipped wares to a lesser extent. EBA

wares are hand-made, burnished and well-baked. Their pastes have mica, lime and plant additives. There are also pastes with small stones, although they are less common. Pastes are grey, brown and red. There are also black pastes, in fewer amounts (Fig. 6).

Figure 6. Dutluca Mound EBA sherds.

2.2.2. Forms (No: 26-58)

EBA wares are very rich in terms of form. Forms such as bowls with inverted rim (no: 26-30), flaring rim deep pots (no:31-34), round pots (no: 36), three legged bowl (no:40), miniature ware (no:41), cut beak spouted piece (no: 35) are the most obvious ones.

Linear and vertical handles and lugs on bowls vary. In addition, vertical lugs have grooved decorations (no: 48-52). A small finger impressed lug is important. These finger imprints were also excavated in other settlements. These finger imprints on vertical lugs should belong to a small hand or should have been made with small fingers (no: 49). Feet (no: 51-54), three legs (no: 40, 55) low and high pedestals (no:

56-58) of bowls and pots commonly found in the region are various. Grooved and fluted decorations were preferred on vessels as decorations. In addition, opaque paint decorations (no: 38-39) and sherds filled with white paste decorations (no: 36-37) are important. Swastika motif on the base of a three legged bowl draws attention (no: 40). There is a miniature ware example with handle, lug and three legs. It is also important for showing a fine workmanship with its grooved decorations on the outer surface (no: 41). The spiral circle decorated pieces in relief form on the body should be evaluated separately (no: 42-44). Apart from these, some loom weights point to textile production in the settlement (no: 45-47). The grooved decoration in one of these loom weights is filled with white paste (no: 45) (Fig. 7).

Figure 7. Dutluca Mound EBA sherds.

Bowls with inverted rim are (no: 26-30) identical to Beycesultan EBA 2 pottery, level XV (Lloyd and Mellaart, 1962) and round pot (no: 36) Yortan wares (Kamil, 1982) and there are similar forms in Uşak Archaeology Museum (Hüryılmaz, 1997).

There is swastika motif under the three legged bowl (no: 40) (Fig. 8). Swastika motif is also found on the base of a pot in Beycesultan. This pot with a plain base does not have three legs. Although it is different in terms of both form and motif, it is present in EBA 2, level XV, Beycesultan (Lloyd and Mellaart, 1962). Swastika motif, which has been seen in Anatolia since the Neolithic Age, has been found on many objects such as sherds, loom weights and idols (Taçyıldız, 2016). The ware found in Dutluca should be dated back to EBA II period. It is possible to see the rich examples of swastika motif in Troia. This motif was

found on spheres, wares and loom weights in Troia (Schliemann, 1881; Blegen et al., 1950). A beak spouted and three legged jug Yortan (EBA II) (Kamil, 1982), a black slipped and three legged pot in Beycesultan EBA II (level XIV) and the base of a grey slipped, linear groove decorated and flat based pot in EBA II (level XV) layer also have swastika motif (Lloyd and Mellaart, 1962). Both examples are different from that in Dutluca. There are also various examples in Karataş-Semayük (Mellink, 1965). The decorations on a grey slipped ware dated back to EBA III in Tarsus-Gözlükule are partly similar to those in Dutluca (Goldman, 1956). However, the decorations in Dutluca are on the base part.

Figure 8. Dutluca Mound bowl with swastika decoration.

Cut beak spouted piece (no: 35) was found in Beycesultan EBA 2, level XVI (Lloyd and Mellaart, 1962), Yortan jugs (Kamil, 1982) and Karataş-

Semayük EBA cemetery finds (Mellink, 1963). Three legged wares have been used extensively in West Anatolia throughout EBA (Sarı and Arslan, 2017). Feet

(no: 51-54) are similar to Troy I (Blegen et al., 1950), Beycesultan EBA 2 (Lloyd and Mellaart, 1962), Yortan (Kamil, 1982). They are used commonly on wares in West Anatolia in EBA. Low and high pedestals (no: 56-58) are found in Troy I and Beycesultan (Blegen et al., 1950).

Spiral circle decorated pieces (no: 42-44) (Fig. 9), J. Mellaart found sherds with spiral motif in some settlements in up Meander Valley. He stated that these spiral motifs may have Cyclad origin (Mellaart, 1954).

There are four spiral stamps on a sherd in Lerna (Early Helladic Period). There was stamp shape on the sherd in Lerna, while there were reliefs in Dutluca. They are very similar in terms of motifs (Caskey, 1958; Caskey 1959). Although not completely identical, it is known that there is a similar relief in Beycesultan EBA II (level XVI) (Lloyd and Mellaart, 1962) and Demircihöyük to the concentric circle relief on a thick-walled body fragment (Efe, 1988).

Figure 9. Dutluca Mound spiral circle decorated pieces.

There are concentric circle and spiral impressed examples in some settlements in up Meander valley (Mellaart, 1954). The ones in Dutluca are not impressed, they are relief decorated. The concentric circle shaped reliefs in Dutluca are similar to the shapes in Neolithic stamps. However, the ones in Dutluca are on a thick-walled body. Concentric circles and spiral motifs are known from Neolithic Age stamps (Lichter,

2005). They are important in terms of the continuation of a tradition from 8000-7000 B.C.E (Lichter, 2005) in 3000 B.C.E in EBA and in terms of showing this. Dutluca concentric circle motifs should probably belong to pithos and date back to EBA II period. Chronological table of EBA settlements are given in the Table 2.

Table 2. Chronological table of EBA settlements of layers.

Site	EBA III 2000-2400BC	EBA II 2400-2700BC	EBA I 2700-3000BC	References
Troia	IV	III- II	I	(Blegen et al., 1950)
Limantepe	IV	V	VI	(Aykurt and Erkanal, 2016)
Beycesultan	VIII	XIII	XVII - XX	(Lloyd and Mellaart, 1962)
Yortan		A		(Kamil, 1982)
Demircihöyük	Q	I	D	(Efe, 1988)
Kusura	C	B	A	(Lamb, 1937)
Karataş-Semayük	V	IV	III	(Mellink, 1965)
Gözlükule	III	II	I	(Goldman, 1956)

2.3. Middle and Late Bronze Age (No: 59-65)

MBA and LBA sherds were also found in upper parts of Dutluca Mound. The excavation of MBA and LBA sherds in the agricultural areas on the upper parts is important in terms of showing that there are earlier sherds in lower layers and giving an idea about the layers of the mound.

There are many settlements in Western Anatolia in the Early Bronze Age. However, there is a great decrease in the number of Middle Bronze Age and Late Bronze Age settlements in the region. For this reason, the existence of MBA and LBA settlements and the presence of sherds from this period indicate the cultural continuity in this settlement. Beycesultan Mound has an important place in terms of MBA and LBA studies in Western Anatolia. Beycesultan is an important settlement that has continuity in the MBA and LBA periods starting from the Late Chalcolithic Age (Lloyd and Mellaart, 1965). The Dutluca region is located not far from Beycesultan. The region where Beycesultan is located in the south of Dutluca is in the upper parts of the Meander valley (Abay et al., 2020). It reveals that pottery production in the Upper Meander valley settlements in the Middle Bronze Age was

made using similar production technologies and locally produced (Semiz et al., 2018). We can evaluate the MBA and LBA of the Dutluca region in this context due to its proximity with the Upper Meander Valley.

On the western Anatolian shores, Troia (Blegen et al., 1953) and Limantepe settlements are important port settlements for the MBA and after. These settlements also have cultural relations with the Aegean Islands and Greece (Aykurt and Erkanal, 2016).

2.3.1. Ware groups

All of these wares are made of wheel except one (no: 59). One piece (no: 59) is hand-made and it signifies transition to MBA from EBA. They are all burnished and well-baked. There is also a grey slipped piece among these brown and red slipped wares. The paste is red and brown to a lesser extent. The paste has mica additives in the paste. Half of them have lime additives, while very few have small stone additives. These wares do not have plant additives (Fig. 10).

Figure 10. Dutluca Mound Middle and Late Bronze Age sherds.

2.3.2. Forms (No: 59-65)

The form consists of bowls. The example with round body and groove decoration (no: 59) show the transition to MBA. Other bowls have thickened rim and also neck. One of them is found to have lug on the rim (no: 64). MBA forms are similar to Kusura C

forms (Lamb, 1937), Beycesultan EBA 3a (Lloyd and Mellaart, 1962), level XII-XI, Beycesultan V (MBA) (Lloyd and Mellaart, 1965). A piece that we considered as lid is important (no: 65). This lid which has a lug and groove decorations on the outside is the only example (Fig. 11).

Figure 11. Dutluca Mound Middle and Late Bronze Age sherds.

3. ADATEPE

Adatepe is located on the northeast of Ulubey town, 2.5-3 km southeast of Dutluca village and Dutluca mound. It is a big hill rocky hill. Adatepe is a settlement located on a natural hill on the east shore

of Yavu stream. The settlement is on a natural hill 30 m high and 250 m long extending east-west in Ulubey Canyon. Since there are agricultural areas on the base of the settlement, it attracts attention (Fig. 12).

Figure 12. View of Adatepe and yavu stream.

Neolithic, Chalcolithic, EBA, Hellenistic and Roman sherds, obsidian blades, flint tools and chips have been found in the settlement. Especially quality Early Chalcolithic Age painted ceramics are concentrated on the south slopes of the settlement. The settlement extends to Yavu stream. Sherds are concentrated on south slopes. Since south slopes are curved, shreds have flowed down. The whole settlement has sherds; however, they are less in other parts since they are covered with grass.

Adatepe is at the start of Ulubey canyons and since it is inside the canyon, it has an altitude of 776 m. Dutluca mound has an altitude of 846 m. This difference results from the decrease in height in the canyon area. For this reason, Adatepe is lower and it is not possible to see it from the lowland. When we follow Yavu stream south from Adatepe, it is connected with

Figure 13. Adatepe pits.

It is difficult to say for sure for what purposes the 6 pits on the west of Adatepe and 9 mass pits on the terraces towards Yavu stream were made. These can have been made for cult or religious purposes or paint production. What is certain is they have close size and depth and they form a unity. These pits which are not very deep and large are too small for storage. The settlement on Yavu stream meets its water need from there. For this reason, we think that they must have been made for cult purposes. Another option is that they may have been made to produce paint for Early Chalcolithic age wares made locally in Adatepe and for paint decorations of wares (Fig. 14).

Köseler mound on the Yavu stream shore 1,5 km south. Köseler mound is located in EBA, it is a wide EBA settlement and there is a pithos cemetery right next to it. Since there are relatively few EBA sherds in Adatepe, Köseler mound and Dutluca mound should be connected. The fact that there were fewer settlements in Adatepe after Chalcolithic age brings to mind that for some reason, the population became dense in Köseler mound 1,5 km on the south and Dutluca mound settlement 2.5 km east. EBA sherds are intense in Dutluca mound and Köseler mound.

6 circular small pits were carved on the west end of the settlement. These pits are 10 cm in diameter and 8 cm deep and built in a specific order. In addition, we found new pits in 2018 a little further down. These pits were made on the rocks above the terraces on the west side and in a specific order (Fig. 13).

Figure 14. Adatepe pits.

We also do not know whether there are similar pits in other points of Adatepe. It is possible that there are in parts underground. The ones we found are on bed-rocks on the west part with no soil. We think that more pits must have been built. Adatepe is on Yavu stream shore. There are barns under rocks on the northwest end of the settlement on stream shore. These barns are still used as animal shelters by shepherds. However, this does not give an idea about how or with what purposes they may have been used in prehistoric period (Fig. 15).

Figure 15. Adatepe barns.

3.1. Neolithic and Chalcolithic Age (No: 66-195)

There are large numbers of Neolithic and Chalcolithic sherds in Adatepe settlement. Sherds have been found intensely especially in the south slopes of the settlement. Sherds found here consist of monochrome and polychrome sherds.

3.1.1. Monochrome Pottery (No: 66-113, 146-155, 191-195)

3.1.1.1. Ware groups

The largest group in monochrome sherds consists of red slipped wares. Red slipped wares constitute

more than half. There were 5 purplish red or purple slipped pieces among these red slipped wares and they were included in this group. The second largest group constitutes more than 1/3 and brown slipped wares. The group consists of grey slipped wares to a lesser extent. The wares of this group are handmade and burnished and they are well-baked. Very few have multi-color on their surface (Fig. 16). The paste mostly (about 3/4) have brown and red colors. Although less, a significant part (about 1/4) has grey paste. Although very few, the presence of those with black paste is also important. The pastes have mica and lime additives. Almost half have small stone additives. Very few have plant additives.

Figure 16. Adatepe monochrome sherds.

3.1.1.2. Forms

Ali There is also variety in terms of form. Open forms are deep, shallow and plain (no: 66-70), while closed forms (no: 71-74) are distinct. These consist of bowls and pots. In addition, necked sherds (no: 75-78), deep sherds (no: 79-93), open rimmed sherds (no: 94-104) and deep sherds (no: 105-113) are important

in terms of variety (Fig. 17). Linear and vertical lugs have various sizes (no: 146-153). There is also an example with lug on the rim (no: 79). The bases are flat (no: 154-155) (Fig. 18). However, straw traces are clearly visible at the lower part of one of the bases (no: 154). Grooved and fluted decorations draw attention on some body sherds (no: 109, 191-195).

Figure 17. Adatepe monochrome sherds.

Figure 18. Adatepe lugs and bases.

Similar open forms (no: 66-70) are found in Yeşilova mound III. 4 layers (Neolithic 6000-5730 B.C.E) on west Anatolian shores (Derin et al., 2009), Ulucak 4c- Neolithic (Çilingiroğlu, 2009), Eskişehir Orman Fidanlığı I-II (Efe, 2001), Asmainler (EC) (Efe, 1989-1990), Kanlıtaş (EC) (Şahin, 2014), Lakes region Kuruçay 12, layers (EN), Kuruçay 11, layers, (LN), Kuruçay 7, layers (EC) (Duru, 1994). Similar closed forms (no: 71-74) are found in Ege Gübre Neolithic (Sağlamtimur, 2012), Çukuriçi mound IX (LN) (Horejs, 2012), Kuruçay 12, layers, (EN) (Duru, 1994), similar pottery (no:79-93) are found in Asmainler (EC) (Efe, 1989-1990), Kanlıtaş (EC) (Şahin, 2014), Kuruçay 13, layers (EN), Kuruçay 11, layers, (LN) (Duru, 1994), Can Hasan layers 7-4 (LN) bowls (French, 2005), similar open rimmed sherds (no: 94-104) are found in Ulucak mound IVf- Neolithic (Çilingiroğlu, 2009), Kanlıtaş (EC) (Şahin, 2014), Kuruçay 13, layers (EN), Kuruçay 7, layers (EC) (Duru, 1994).

Similar linear and vertical lugs (no:146-153) are found in Kanlıtaş (EC) (Şahin, 2014), Höyücek Temple period (EN) lugs (Duru and Umurtak, 2005), Kuruçay 13, layers (EN), Kuruçay 11, layers (LN), similar flat bases (no:154-155) are found in Kuruçay 13, layers (EN), Kuruçay 10-9, layers (EC) (Duru, 1994), similar straw traces (no: 154) are found in Ege Gübre Chalcolithic age bases (Yazıcı, 2009) and Gülpınar Chalcolithic age bases (5000 B.C.E) (Ozdemir, 2012).

3.1.2. Polychrome Pottery (No: 114-145, 156-190)

The most prominent ware group in Adatepe consists of polychrome pottery. The most obvious feature of this group is that while only the interior parts of some pottery have painted decorations, only the exterior parts of some have painted decorations. There is also another group with painted decorations on both interior and exterior surface.

3.1.2.1. Ware groups

The largest groups among painted sherds consist of pink-cream slipped wares (about half). There is a significant amount of red slipped and brown slipped wares. There are also grey slipped wares, to a lesser extent. There are also white slipped wares. Another important point is that the slips on the interior surface and the exterior surface of some pottery show differences. For example, a bowl which has a cream slipped

interior surface can have a red slipped exterior surface (no: 114). There are also examples with grey slipped interior surface and white slipped exterior surface (no: 126) and white slipped interior surface and brown slipped exterior surface (no: 170). Apart from these, there are also wares with different interior and exterior slips.

Pastes mostly have red and brown tones. Grey pastes exist with a rate of $\frac{1}{4}$ and they are in significant numbers. There are also cream pastes, although very few. The handmade wares of this group are well baked. Almost all of the pastes have mica additive. More than $\frac{2}{3}$ have lime additive. There are few wares with small stone additive. A few samples were found to have plant additive (Fig. 19).

Figure 19. Photomicrograph from the (a) quartz, rock fragment, (b) rock fragment, (c) muscovite (d) quartz, rock fragment, sand particle.

It was found that painted decorations were on the interior, exterior surface and on both surfaces. There are also sherds with painted decorations on rims. A great majority of painted decorations are red. It can also be seen that brown painted decorations were used to a lesser extent. The least number of samples were samples with grey-black painted decorations. One sherd was found to have yellow painted decorations. It is very important that painted decorations of different colors were applied on cream, red, brown and grey slips. Adatepe wares are very different from red on cream wares of Hacilar. Adatepe wares do not have fantastic decorations of Hacilar (Fig. 20).

Figure 20. Adatepe painted sherds.

There are also differences in the application of painted decorations. Some of the painted decorations were not made carefully and they gave the impression that less paint was used. Decorations were made first; however, weak colors draw attention. Others are darker where the application ends. The tool, brush or straw used in painting was used with not much care or not intensively. Some pieces give the impression that they were painted with cane. For example, cream slip was well applied. However, painted decorations are not as dark and regular as those in Hacilar. This should be considered as the basic difference. The masters in Adatepe worked with a different style. Paint decorations vary with horizontal, vertical and diago-

nal bands in the form of zigzag, chevron and scanning. Paint decoration was made on the inner part of a pot by pressing the finger (no: 136). All these should be considered as local style differences, unlike Hacilar.

3.1.2.2. Forms

Use this painted group consists of open form plate-bowls (no: 114-129), incurved bowls (no: 130-132) (Fig. 21), open rim and necked bowls (no: 133-139), deep forms (no: 140-141), open and round forms (no: 142-145) (Fig. 22), paint decorated flat base sherds (no: 156) and sherds with paint decorated body (no: 157-190) (Fig. 23).

Figure 21. Adatepe painted sherds.

Figure 22. Adatepe painted sherds.

Some of the bowls have lug (no: 130-131). There is a hole on the body in one of the pieces (no: 142). Apart from painted decorations, there are also few examples with grooved decoration (no: 191-195) (Fig. 24). Sherds with paint decorated body (no: 157-190) are similar to web combing decorations Kuruçay 11. layers (LN), Kuruçay 10 and 9 layers (EC) (Duru, 1994).

Although we could not find identical similars of Adatepe sherds, it is possible to compare them with

its contemporary centres such as Hacilar, Kuruçay, Can Hasan. Adatepe Early Chalcolithic Age paint decoration tradition has continued with its local features. Since there are so many painted sherds on surface, we believe that significant results will be found if excavations are made.

Figure 23. Adatepe painted sherds.

Figure 24. Adatepe painted sherds.

4. DISCUSSION

Excavations on prehistoric periods have not been carried out in Uşak, yet. For this reason, an excavation should be carried out to illuminate the prehistory of the region. Thus, an excavation to be carried out in Dutluca or Adatepe is important. With this, it will be possible to reach data to reveal the connections between Western Anatolia and Central Anatolia, not only Central Western Anatolia. It is thought that conducting studies to show the relationships or differences between Neolithic cultures in the northwest of Turkey and Neolithic cultures in Lakes region in the

south will shed light on results that will reveal Neolithic and Chalcolithic Age cultural development and interactions within the context of Western Anatolia.

While information is limited after the Middle Palaeolithic in Uşak, it can be seen that settlements began to increase after Neolithic Age. However, there are not enough findings or data to make an evaluation about pre-Neolithic. For this reason, we cannot say anything about Neolithic and pre-Neolithic. As in many settlements in Uşak region, it is difficult to find out the presence of lower levels of culture as a result of the late culture levels covering the early settlements in Dutluca region. This situation exists in many

settlements in West Anatolia. It should be considered that Neolithic settlements exist under the alluvial deposit covered by settlements of the Early Bronze Age and later periods.

It has been evaluated that most of the Neolithic and Early Chalcolithic settlements in up Meander Basin are on plains, while less are on mountains. These settlements with an altitude of 860 and 1081 metres are spread over an area of 1-1.5 hectares (Dedeoğlu, 2014). It has been shown that the settlements have existed since the Early Chalcolithic Age and that they are similar to Hacilar Lakes region. Late Neolithic and Early Chalcolithic Age settlements are scattered in the bottom land or lake shore. Hacilar painted ceramic has been found in these settlements (Abay and Dedeoğlu, 2007).

Dutluca mound and Adatepe settlements are close to Büyük Menderes Valley (Meander). For this reason, they are related with the settlements in up Menderes Valley. Especially the similarities between Selcen-Örenarası settlement and monochrome pottery forms indicate relations. However, it is difficult to say this for painted pottery. There is no data to make evaluations for paint decorated pottery in Selcen-Örenarası. However, thanks to the painted pottery obtained from the settlements in up Menderes Valley, it can be seen that the basin forms a cultural integrity with the Lakes Region (Dedeoğlu and Ozan, 2016).

Adatepe is on the shore of Yavu stream. Yavu stream flows south, joins with Banaz stream and connects to Büyük Menderes River (Meander). One of the differentiating features of Adatepe is that it is located on a rocky hill in the valley eroded by Yavu stream. The top of the rock, which is not too high for settlement, is very suitable for settlement and the settlement also made use of the facilities offered by Yavu stream on the west. There is no data to help us know how the settlement was used in prehistoric period due to the alluvial fill in the flat area at the bottom of the rocky hill, that is, on the skirts of the settlement. However, this area is very suitable for agricultural activities the settlement needs. Yavu stream, which includes the settlement, is located in Ulubey canyons in the south. The area where the canyons start is in valley which is not too deep. There are wide flat areas around Adatepe and Yavu stream and they are very suitable for obtaining raw material. While most of the Neolithic or Early Chalcolithic settlements are located on flat areas, Adatepe is on a natural hill.

Since Adatepe's surroundings are covered with alluvial fill, residents are engaged in agriculture nowadays. It is not possible to find out whether these parts were used in earlier periods or how they were used if they were used at all. Perhaps the area where the hill is located is enough to accommodate the population

of the settlement. In any way, it is possible that the surroundings of Adatepe have been used in line with the needs. However, an exploration should be conducted to support these.

One of the remarkable finds in Adatepe is the small pits on the west side of the hill and on the bedrock towards Yavu stream. These were pits carved on the bedrock symmetrically in a certain order and it should be emphasized that they were made for holy or religious purposes or paint production.

More broadly, Adatepe is connected with Yavu stream and Ulubey canyons and other settlements in Uşak plain. On the south, it is connected to Meander with Banaz stream. We can compare Adatepe partly with Eskişehir Kanlıtaş as a settlement. Kanlıtaş is not completely on a hill, it is also located on slopes. However, Adatepe is completely on a hill in a canyon. There are no finds in the flat area around Adatepe. Perhaps the soil was buried under the filling, we don't know about this. However, it is a location completely on the hill. There is no soil filling on the rocky area on the west side of Adatepe towards Yavu stream. Perhaps it was left empty deliberately. However, small pits were also opened here and they were made deliberately. The pits in Adatepe were made in a specific way and with a specific order.

Unlike many settlements in Anatolia, Kanlıtaş is located on a large independent bedrock elevation in the valley. For this reason, while a very large filling is not expected at the top of the mounds, it was observed in the excavations at the top of the settlement that the rocks were cut and the site was built directly. The fact that it was surrounded with thick terrace walls in places shows that the settlement is deeper than we expected (Türkcan, 2015). Kanlıtaş is in a large valley. However, Adatepe is in a narrow area in the canyon. For now, there is no other example of Adatepe.

Due to the location of Yavu stream and the presence of wide agricultural areas, there have been settlements in Dutluca mound since Early Neolithic. The density of Early Neolithic sherds in Adatepe is the main factor in preferring this area as settlement. Perhaps, people settled in Adatepe when the population in Dutluca mound increased or due to social reasons. The fact that Köselier mound was close to Adatepe in EBA brings to mind that people settled in Köselier mound in EBA due to different reasons because EBA sherds are not intense in Adatepe. In any way, since Dutluca mound, Adatepe and Köselier mound were located close to each other, it is inevitable for them to be culturally connected.

J. Mellaart mentioned a ceramic different from Hacilar Early Chalcolithic painted sherds as Dutluca sherds. However, it is not known whether he meant Adatepe or Dutluca mound or both by saying Dutluca. However, considering that Dutluca mound

was not much destructed in 1970s, it is very probable that Mellart pointed to Adatepe because there are a large number of painted ceramics in Adatepe and they flowed down as a result of wear. Similarly, T. Efe examined Dutluca with Uşak Museum in 1999. He did not find Early Chalcolithic in Dutluca mound; however, he collected a large number of Early Chalcolithic Age painted sherds in Adatepe (Efe, 2001). However, we think that both researchers must have pointed to Adatepe as Dutluca. However, in our study we showed that settlement existed in Dutluca mound since Early Neolithic Age.

While distributing the Hacilar pottery, James Mellaart evaluated Dutluca in Uşak region as a separate group. In his map, Hacilar VI can be seen to spread in a wide area to Chios Island in West Anatolia. He distributes Hacilar I painted wares in southwest Anatolia. The maps here evaluate Hacilar I painted wares as a separate group and Dutluca ware as a separate group (Mellaart, 1970).

Hacilar VI monochrome wares are distributed in a wide area. Hacilar I painted wares can be seen in Akhisar and Ayio Gala in Chios. Hacilar VI type wares were also found in Uşak region. Surveys conducted showed Hacilar VI type monochrome wares and red on cream and thick linear lined examples. However, they were not published (Mellaart, 1970). Dutluca wares were not found in Hacilar (Mellaart, 1970). Although Hacilar affected Western Anatolia, we don't know about the effects of Dutluca and Adatepe mounds on other regions. Perhaps they can be compared with Afyonkarahisar region, which is the closest (Koçak and Bilgin, 2010).

Mellart evaluates and accepts Dutluca ware completely different from Hacilar I ware. Turan Efe visited Dutluca in 1999. He stated that he could not find any Early Chalcolithic sherds in Dutluca mound next to the village and stated that there were no Early Chalcolithic finds. However, he found Early Chalcolithic age sherds in Adatepe, which is 3 km on the west. However, Adatepe does not exist on J. Mellart map. It is mentioned as Dutluca. Turan Efe says that perhaps J. Mellart was talking about Adatepe when he referred to materials as Dutluca. Adatepe wares are really very interesting. Turan Efe says Dutluca wares are more similar to Hacilar culture than north areas and that they are closely related. There are a large number of red painted sherds in Adatepe and some of the paints are applied directly to surface. Others are painted on cream slip. In general, linear motifs, mostly chevrons and linear zigzags show that they are not earlier than Hacilar I. The wares have dapples as a result of paint slips and partial darkening (Efe, 2001).

The most obvious ware group of Early Chalcolithic age ceramic material in Aslanapa culture is purplish-

red wares (Efe, 1993). Aslanapa culture is represented with purplish-red slipped wares. Purplish-red slipped wares of Aslanapa culture are between Hacilar and Porsuk regions. Porsuk culture consists of dark surface burnished wares. Porsuk culture affected Vinça culture in Balkans (Efe, 2002).

It is stated that Dutluca ware group in Uşak are similar to characteristic wares in Hacilar I layer. Adatepe settlement is also important in terms of obtaining purplish-red slipped wares of Porsuk culture. In addition, it is clear that there were influences as a result of the groove decorated samples having been found in this region as well as ware groups (Efe, 2001). There are purplish-red slipped wares in Uşak region and Adatepe. This indicates that Uşak region is influenced by the surrounding culture regions. Uşak is influenced by other regions; however, we do not know about its influences on other regions. However, it is possible to explain this with Uşak's geographical location.

Lakes Region (Hacilar) Early Chalcolithic Age painted tradition does not exist intensely in settlements in the Aegean region. However, monochrome pottery continues in Aegean shores in Late Neolithic-Early Chalcolithic Age (Dedeoğlu and Ozan, 2016). Lakes Region painted pottery exists in Kütahya and Eskişehir to the north (Seeher, 1987). The Akmakça settlement, where the Neolithic cultures of Hacilar-Lakes region spread in the north, is in the Gediz plain and this place is in the north of Uşak province. Porsuk valley in which Fikirtepe culture is spread is on the north of Uşak (Efe, 1995). Dutluca region settlements between these cultures are important for this reason. Demircihöyük is also within Fikirtepe culture; however, there isn't enough data for Uşak region. J. Mellaart thinks that black on red pottery is influenced by Konya-Akşehir region (Mellaart, 1975). Only one black on red sherd was found in Orman Fidanlığı, Early Chalcolithic Age, Stage IV, (Efe, 2001).

Neolithic Age settlements exist in Uşak, Selçikler, Altıntaş, around Banaz. Painted ceramics are found in Afyonkarahisar and other places. However, they are not as intense as Adatepe. For this reason, it is not easy to make evaluation.

Dutluca has given finds continuously from Neolithic Age to our day. With the surveys conducted here, it will be possible to understand the 9000-long process as a whole. As a result of the investigations to be conducted in Dutluca or Adatepe, important results will arise to understand the Chalcolithic Age. An excavation should be carried out here to show the relationships between Lakes Region-Hacilar in the south and Fikirtepe in the north and also between Central Anatolia, Çatalhöyük and Western Anatolia. It is an important centre for understanding the development of painted ceramic. We agree with J. Mellaart

that Dutluca region wares are different from Hacilar painted wares.

5. CONCLUSION

There is an uninterrupted 9.000-year-old settlement in Dutluca mound starting from Early Neolithic period to the present day. In Neolithic age, Dutluca region settlements were associated with Western Anatolia shores, Lakes Region and Eskişehir-Kütahya region. Monochrome ceramics have similar features to those in these regions. However, painted Early Chalcolithic ceramic shows a different decomposition. One of the points that make Adatepe important is the fact that there are a large number of painted sherds. There are not as many painted wares as Adatepe on the surfaces of other settlements. Since it is on a rocky area, there are a large number of paint decorated sherds on hills towards slopes-especially south slopes. Such a large number of Early Chalcolithic painted pottery has not been detected in any other settlement in Western Anatolia, except for the Lakes Region. The amount of painted wares detected in settlements on the Western Anatolian coast is small. In Adatepe, it is densely located on the surface of the settlement. This situation shows that there was intensive production of painted wares in the Early Chalcolithic Age in Adatepe.

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Adatepe shows its own development instead of imitating Hacilar paint. Even if they are inspired from Hacilar, paint decorations were different. The main difference results from applying the paint. Adatepe's Early Chalcolithic Age paints constitute a whole. Dutluca Chalcolithic paints are different. Hacilar dark red on cream painted potteries are distinct; however, there are light red on cream potteries in Dutluca. Thick band decoration is almost non-existent in Dutluca. Distinct anthropomorphic paint decorations of Hacilar do not exist in Dutluca. These differences show that the Dutluca region culturally differed in the Early Chalcolithic Age and revealed its own style.

The presence of purplish red slipped wares in the north in Dutluca region represents the relationships with surrounding cultural regions. There is no relation with the Fikirtepe culture, which is located further north. Dutluca region is in the same cultural region with Beycesultan in EBA. Dutluca region, which was an uninterrupted settlement from Neolithic to our day, is in a position with important clues in determining the borders of other cultural regions. It is possible to conclude that the Dutluca region can be considered as a separate cultural region in the context of the Early Chalcolithic Age, such as the Lakes Region, Fikirtepe, and the West Anatolian shores.

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